

THE SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL FOUNDATIONS FOR PREVENTING SOCIALLY DANGEROUS BEHAVIOR AMONG STUDENTS AND YOUTH

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a scientific and theoretical analysis of a system of spiritual technologies aimed at preventing socially dangerous behavior among students and young people in higher education institutions. The research substantiates the role of spiritual and moral education, psychological support, interactive learning, the development of legal awareness, and preventive measures in student socialization, their psychological resilience, and the development of civic responsibility. It also analyzes stressful situations that arise in student life and their connection to socially dangerous behavior, and highlights the potential for developing stress-resistant behavior through spiritual technologies.

Introduction. In the process of spiritually and educationally nurturing young people, the system of spiritual technologies aimed at preventing socially dangerous behavior in higher education institutions encompasses a set of comprehensive mechanisms that support students' socialization. Primarily, this system serves to cultivate in students a sense of patriotism, justice, conscientiousness, and social responsibility through spiritual and moral education. These qualities function as mechanisms of internal regulation and moral restraint within students' behavior.

Psychological support mechanisms are directed toward enhancing students' resilience to stress, ensuring emotional stability, and strengthening adaptability in social relations. During the period of study, academic workload, examination pressure, competition, adaptation to a new social environment, and uncertainties related to future professional activities generate stress-inducing situations. If such conditions are not identified and addressed in a timely manner, they may create a psychological foundation for socially dangerous behavior.

From this perspective, interactive forms of education and upbringing—such as training sessions, group discussions, debates, leadership workshops, and collective activities—play a significant role in developing cooperation, social responsibility, and the values of social ethics among students. The development of civic and legal consciousness fosters respect for the law, legal accountability, and an internalized need to act lawfully within society.

Furthermore, through simulated preventive measures, socially dangerous situations and their potential consequences are analyzed, thereby cultivating students' awareness, responsibility, and independent decision-making skills. As a result, the system of spiritual

technologies contributes to a significant reduction in students' propensity toward socially dangerous actions by fostering a stable civic position, psychological well-being, and social responsibility.

On January 19, 2021, during a videoconference meeting chaired by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, issues concerning the improvement of the system of spiritual and educational work and the strengthening of cooperation between state and public organizations were discussed. The President emphasized: "The declining role of the public in youth upbringing is a matter of concern for all of us. In the past, we adhered to the proverb, 'Seven neighborhoods are parents to one child.' Not only parents, but also community members, elders, and intellectuals felt responsible for the morality and education of our sons and daughters. As a result, conflicts, hooliganism, and alcohol abuse among youth were rare in neighborhoods, and family divorces were less frequent. Representatives of the older generation taught young people diligence, thrift, and the maintenance of public order" [1].

These statements highlight the importance of the neighborhood community (mahalla), the public, and the family in the upbringing of students and youth, as well as the necessity of comprehensive measures implemented through a system of spiritual technologies to prevent socially dangerous behavior. In higher education institutions, the system of spiritual technologies is aimed at fostering social responsibility and moral values among students. Through this system, students are protected from socially dangerous actions, educated within a healthy socio-emotional environment, and developed as stable individuals actively participating in society.

Literature Review and Methods. The issues of spirituality and enlightenment have long been significant factors in the social development of our country. The spirituality and moral upbringing of youth, as well as the role of social relations in personality formation, have been thoroughly elucidated in the rich scientific and spiritual heritage of Eastern thinkers. In particular, the works of Imam al-Bukhari, Imam al-Tirmidhi, Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Abu Rayhan al-Biruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Jalal al-Din Rumi, Husayn Voiz Kashifi, Alisher Navoi, Mahmudkhoja Behbudi, Abdulla Avloni, and Abdurauf Fitrat advance the idea of educating the younger generation to become spiritually and morally mature individuals and responsible members of society.

In contemporary research, students' propensity toward socially dangerous behavior in higher education institutions is interpreted as a multifactorial process. Notably, in his Address to the Oliy Majlis (2020), Sh.M. Mirziyoyev emphasized that creating favorable conditions for youth and developing their intellectual and spiritual potential constitute priority directions of state policy [2]. This approach reinforces the importance of educational and spiritual mechanisms in protecting students and youth from socially dangerous behavior.

Ismoilova N.Z. (2020), in her research, analyzed the psychological determinants of developing stress resilience among students and substantiated the direct relationship between stressogenic situations, emotional instability, and socially undesirable behavior [3]. The author emphasizes the necessity of a comprehensive approach to enhancing stress resistance—simultaneously influencing cognitive, affective, conative, and physiological factors.

Akramov A.A. (2016), examining the development of students' civic position based on personality-oriented educational technologies, demonstrates that the integration of spiritual-moral, legal, and social qualities constitutes an important pedagogical resource in preventing socially dangerous behavior [4].

Results and Discussion. The system of spiritual technologies aimed at preventing socially dangerous behavior in higher education institutions includes mechanisms that support students' socialization.

Spiritual and moral education reduces students' propensity toward socially dangerous actions by fostering patriotism, justice, dedication, conscientiousness, and a sense of social responsibility.

Psychological support enhances students' stress resilience, emotional stability, and effectiveness in social interactions, enabling them to become psychologically balanced individuals capable of making socially rational decisions.

Interactive educational and upbringing activities—such as leadership training, group discussions, and club and team-based initiatives—contribute to the formation of cooperation skills, collective responsibility, and the values of social ethics.

The development of civic and legal consciousness involves instilling legal knowledge and adherence to the law, thereby encouraging students to act within lawful frameworks in society.

Simulated preventive measures provide systematic information about specific examples of socially dangerous behavior and strategies for avoiding them. Through debates, training sessions, and simulated scenarios, students' awareness and sense of responsibility are strengthened.

Thus, student socialization represents an integrative outcome of spiritual and moral values, psychological stability, and civic responsibility. It ensures students' active and positive participation in society, protects them from socially dangerous behavior, and supports their stable personal development. The system of spiritual technologies in higher education institutions is designed to systematically implement this process and to foster a healthy socio-emotional environment among students.

In our country, educating students as competitive and comprehensively developed professionals, and creating all necessary conditions for passionate and motivated young people who aspire to obtain higher education and pursue knowledge, remains one of the key priorities of state policy. In this regard, it is advisable to deepen scientific research aimed at comprehensively studying the psychological determinants of stress resilience among students vulnerable to the negative effects of stress, and at identifying opportunities to form stress-resistant behavior by simultaneously influencing their cognitive, affective, conative, and physiological domains.

Indeed, the period of higher education is characterized by specific stressogenic situations that significantly affect students' psychology and overall performance. These include academic workload and requirements, examination and assessment pressure, competition within courses and faculties, adaptation to a new social environment, separation from family and familiar social surroundings, uncertainty regarding future professional activities, and increasing personal responsibilities.

For some students, these factors become primary contributors to stress, leading to emotional and cognitive difficulties, disrupted sleep patterns, decreased motivation, and reduced activity levels. Nevertheless, the positive aspect lies in the possibility of identifying and managing such conditions through preventive and educational interventions. Psychological training, stress management programs, spiritual and legal education, and social support systems can effectively enhance students' resilience to stress.

Moreover, the impact of stressogenic situations depends on individual characteristics. Students' psychological traits, emotional stability, level of social support, and spiritual-moral preparedness may either protect them from stress or, conversely, intensify its effects. From this perspective, the system of spiritual technologies in higher education institutions aimed at preventing socially dangerous behavior should also include mechanisms for identifying stressogenic situations and providing psychological and spiritual interventions that foster resilience.

In working with students in higher education institutions, it is essential to cultivate specific qualities that ensure the development of a mature civic position, social responsibility, and protection from socially dangerous behavior. Scientific research and analytical observations indicate that, in order to develop a well-formed civic stance, students should effectively acquire the following qualities:

Spiritual and moral qualities: patriotism, internationalism, diligence, dedication, justice, conscientiousness, understanding and supporting state policy, friendship and tolerance, commitment to peace and justice, positive national traits (hospitality, care for children, collectivism, generosity, nobility), active participation in community activities, leadership abilities, and protection of the honor of one's family, educational institution, and academic group.

Volitional qualities: strong character, willpower, psychological resilience, perseverance, determination, patience, the ability to exercise self-control and make effective decisions in various situations, proactivity, and courage.

Intellectual qualities: knowledgeability, competence, inquisitiveness, creativity, independent thinking, analytical ability and resourcefulness, quick thinking, and adaptability.

Physical qualities – being physically healthy and mature, mobility, possessing physical culture, and maintaining a healthy lifestyle.

Ecological qualities – a positive attitude toward nature and the environment, ecological awareness and responsibility, preservation of land and water resources, contribution to the prevention of environmental risks, protection of the flora and fauna of Uzbekistan, and the economical use of energy and natural resources.

Legal qualities – legal consciousness and civic engagement, acceptance of legal and socio-moral norms, respect for state symbols, compliance with laws, and responsibility in legal relations.

Economic qualities – economic awareness, industriousness, commitment to labor and professional activity, entrepreneurship, thriftiness, and knowledge of consumer rights.

Conclusion. In higher education institutions, the prevention of socially dangerous behavior among students is implemented through a system of spiritual technologies. This system

includes spiritual and educational activities, dissemination of information and knowledge, development of leadership and social engagement, обеспечение psychological and emotional stability, and preventive measures aimed at protecting youth from socially dangerous actions. The primary objective is to reduce students' propensity toward socially dangerous behavior by fostering a stable civic position, social responsibility, and spiritual resilience.

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